

**Digital
Citizenship**

Access and Inclusion Course

Readings | Exercises | Case studies | Quizzes

Erasmus+

ATHENS
LIFELONG
LEARNING
INSTITUTE

4 TEAM 4
excellence

SEAL
CYPRUS

Strategic partnership to develop open educational resources for teaching digital citizenship

2019-3-RO01-KA205-078053

DIGCIT

D7 – Digital Citizenship “Access and Inclusion” Course

Revision: v.1.1

Intellectual output	IO2 - Educational Materials for digital citizenship
Activity	Course Curriculum Development
Deliverable lead	Sustainable Education Active Learning – SEAL CYPRUS
Due date	15 March 2021
Authors	Sofronis THEMISTOCLEOUS
Abstract	<p>The module “Access and inclusion” deals with the competences necessary for overcoming different forms of the digital divide and opening digital spaces to minorities and different opinions. Online environments are ideal spaces for expanding multiculturalism and democratic values. They can also, when abused, result in the opposite effects.</p> <p>This course intends to teach participants how to guide themselves and others into more open attitudes and inclusive behaviours to embrace the diversity inherent in the online community and resolve conflicts by expressing themselves in more productive ways while guarding against unproductive divisive attitudes.</p>
Keywords	Model course; digital citizenship; course plan; access; inclusion; prejudices; democracy; unacceptable behaviours; bullying; fake news; education; reflection; case studies

Acknowledgement

This paper has received funding from the European Commission under Grant Agreement—2019-3-RO01-KA205-078053, ERASMUS+ Strategic Partnership project “Strategic partnership to develop open educational resources for teaching digital citizenship”.

Erasmus+

ATHENS
LIFELONG
LEARNING
INSTITUTE4 TEAM 4
excellenceSEAL
CYPRUS

Disclaimer

„The European Commission support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents which reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.”

Copyright notice

© 2020 - 2022 DIGCIT Consortium

The license **Attribution CC BY** lets others distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon your work, even commercially, as long as they credit you for the original creation. This is the most accommodating of licenses offered. Recommended for maximum dissemination and use of licensed materials.

Contents

Introduction	6
1. Module 1 - Introducing the concepts of access and inclusion.....	7
What is access.....	7
What is inclusion.....	8
Why are access and inclusion important.....	10
Case study - Cornwall’s digital inclusion programme	11
Why are access and inclusion skills important	11
Exercise 1: In the other’s shoes	12
2. Module 2 - Are we all prejudiced.....	14
How our mind works.....	14
How to combat prejudice	15
Case Study - The Bogota Doll	16
Why is understanding and reducing prejudice important.....	16
Exercise 2: Strangers no more	17
3. Module 3 - Democracy and the digital.....	19
How democracy works.....	19
How the digital makes democracy better.....	20
Case study - Decide Madrid	21
Why are democracy and the digital important together.....	21
Exercise 3: Democracy at risk	22
4. Module 4 - Trolls and other creatures of the net	24
Unacceptable behaviours, from bullying to fake news	24
What you should know about the dangers of the digital world.....	25
Case study – hacking techniques	26
Why should you beware of using the internet	26
Exercise 4: White hat and black hat hackers	26
5. Module 5 - Become an access and inclusion champion	28
Be the change	28
How to stay safe and protect others	29
A brave new world	29
Case study - Storming of the United States Capitol.....	30
Why is becoming an access an inclusion champion important	30
Exercise 5: Use and abuse.....	31
6. Assessment quizzes.....	33

7. References	37
Appendix	39
Assessment quiz check sheets	39
Instructional design review checklist for youth workers	40
Feedback on topic for students	41

Erasmus+

ATHENS
LIFELONG
LEARNING
INSTITUTE

4 TEAM 4
excellence

SEAL
CYPRUS

Introduction

The module “Access and inclusion” is fundamental to enabling learners’ online voice. More than this, it is crucial to teach learners how to enable other people’s voices so that the overall digital world becomes a more open and accessible environment with numerous positive spillovers into the physical world. This world has its very own rules that must be understood so that access and inclusion can be afforded to all undisturbed.

The Digital Citizenship Educational Handbook of the Council of Europe defines Access and inclusion as: “... access to the digital environment and includes a range of competences that relate not only to overcoming different forms of digital exclusion but also to the skills needed by future citizens to participate in digital spaces that are open to every kind of minority and diversity of opinion.”

As such, the course will impart to participants those necessary skills to fulfil this competence. It will teach learners how to guide themselves and others into more open attitudes and inclusive behaviours to embrace the diversity inherent in the online community and resolve conflicts by expressing oneself in more productive ways while guarding against unproductive divisive attitudes. The skills acquired will thus then translate well into the physical world and their everyday lives.

As such, Access and Inclusion are combined together into one notion of openness. Democracy and acceptance go hand in hand. Anything that would bar Access and Inclusion in all its forms would become an unbearable constraint on Democracy and its humanitarian values such as that of openness and dialogue in the physical plane and vice versa.

The importance of the topic should not be underestimated. The skills acquired here can well be used in the broader spectrum of life. The overall aim, beyond topic-specific knowledge and competences acquired, is to use these to overcome prejudices, inherent in our society by being given the tools to understand them, their impact and how to alter patterns of thought as well as behaviours in ourselves and others. This will turn come to effect positive change that may help overcome those differences that may at times lead to the physical and digital divide.

1. Module 1 - Introducing the concepts of access and inclusion

Snapshot

Summary: This topic deals with the fundamentals of Access and Inclusion as a general concept. It touches upon such issues as why are the two important, and how they relate to each other as well as explores various constraints to them. Students are guided to understand that Access and Inclusion are very important and universal rights that help make the digital environment a more hospitable and productive place for all.

Key Takeaways:

- Understand the concept of access and Inclusion
- Explain the concepts' importance in modern societies
- Describe barriers and restrains to it

What is access

The term access should be understood in terms of both competence and infrastructure. Though for many living in developed countries this may come as a surprise, a vast number of people lack basic access to the internet.

In fact, in 2018 just 50.7% of the world population¹ were internet users with access to the web. In Europe, though the percentage² is much more satisfactory and accounts for 90% of the EU citizens, still this needs to be qualified by two parameters.

¹ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/IT.NET.USER.ZS>

² [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Digital_economy_and_society_statistics_-_households_and_individuals#:~:text=Planned%20article%20update%3A%20September%202021.&text=By%202019%2C%20the%20share%20of,in%202009%20\(55%2025\).](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Digital_economy_and_society_statistics_-_households_and_individuals#:~:text=Planned%20article%20update%3A%20September%202021.&text=By%202019%2C%20the%20share%20of,in%202009%20(55%2025).)

One, this ratio is not equally distributed in member states. In Bulgaria for example the ratio falls as short as 95% and in Luxemburg rises as high as 95% of residents there being internet users. The second is that the EU has an enormous influx of migrants from non-EU countries and especially developing countries which as was said traditionally exhibit a much lower rate of internet usage. This second qualifier brings us to the other aforementioned aspect of the term, that of understanding it as a competence.

There is an abundance of relevant skills here. These can be objective and subjective. For example, skills included in the objective part include things such as:

- Media Skills
- Witting skills
- Communication skills
- Safety skills
- Internet skills
- Netiquette skills
- Search skills
- Navigation skills
- Browsing skills

However, access includes a personal element as well. It means making ourselves accessible to others. There are several ways to accomplish this, including:

- Being generally friendly
- Showing interest in others
- Being an active listener
- Offering our help even when not requested
- Being open about how we feel
- Inviting others to share their opinion
- Complementing when something deserves praise
- Avoiding inside jokes
- Explaining our point of view
- Speaking up when we see instances that limit access

When we require access, we must also grant it. We are always free to disagree with anyone we like and though we are entitled to our own opinion we are not entitled to our own facts. This however does not mean we must take an impersonal outlook on people who may be misguided on some issues. Instead, a mentor attempt must be made by trying to explain calmly our point of view and making room for the fact that we may be also mistaken. Less we forget that not everyone has internet access and a bundle of experience.

Naturally, people with no internet access will lack internet access related skills. This course through the module “Access and Inclusion” aims to address this in both ensuring that relevant access competencies are acquired by participants and that the competencies’ importance is understood.

What is inclusion

The world is a vast chaotic place. No matter how much we try to make sense of it we can only go so far. This is even more true when it comes to the endless labyrinth of its digital counterpart, the internet.

A huge surge in technology brought with it a vast number of applications. These range from platforms, to games, mobile apps, and social media to blended learning environments, and more. All these require the necessary skills to navigate. However, it is the responsibility of the country to ensure that its citizens and those living within it are not left behind. This is especially so with those groups more prone to becoming marginalized, such as the elderly, migrants, and people with disabilities.

Democracy cannot work if everyone does not have a voice. To this inclusion is critical. More than empowerment in the sense of one possessing the necessary skills to make their voice heard, others must be willing to accept them and help ensure that they have a place on the digital and physical table. This is inclusion. Only by understanding the importance of Inclusion and the contribution it makes to digital democracy can this be done.

Understanding inclusion also means understanding and accepting diversity. This is not an innate ability for most. As we will see later, our own minds are designed in a certain way that dates back to the time when we lived in small groups and being overly cautious towards those outside of our group was more beneficial than harmful. This however now changed and we must help our minds to keep up with these changes.

According to³ James Stanfield, doing this means incorporating the following concepts into your life:

- **Celebrate Diversity:** Pay attention to the materials you use in class. Do they depict children from a variety of backgrounds and with varying abilities? How do books, videos, and other materials portray children with special needs? Celebrate the diversity in your classroom and teach your students to do the same.
- **Educate Yourself:** Educate yourself about the specific disabilities any of the students you work with have. You can then educate your students. Education leads to understanding which then leads to compassion and connection.
- **Encourage Interaction:** Give students opportunities to interact with each other so they can build friendships and a sense of community.
- **Strengths-Based Approach:** Everyone has strengths and weaknesses. Help kids develop their strengths and see that kids with special needs have strengths too. Focus on progress, no matter how small.
- **Differentiate Instruction:** When teachers differentiate all students can participate and work at their current ability.
- **Make Objectives Clear:** Posting and reviewing objectives in age-appropriate language helps all students achieve the desired objective of each lesson. It is especially helpful for kids with special needs.
- **Adapt:** Teachers are masters at adapting. We watch our students and constantly assess; slowing down when they don't understand something and then speeding up when it's clear they've already got it. We challenge those that are ready for more and provide extra support to those that need it.
- **Explicit Teaching and Modeling:** Model for students and gradually turn the responsibility over to the student. The "I do, We do, You do" approach is especially beneficial to kids with special needs; it gives them the support they need to keep up with traditional classroom activities.
- **Have a Positive Attitude:** As the teacher, your positive attitude about inclusion sets the tone for the rest of the class.

³ <https://stanfield.com/11-strategies-promote-inclusion-in-the-classroom/>

These are fundamentals for both educators and learners. They are good examples that can translate well to all walks of life. From being a teacher yourself to running a business working to develop such competencies will ensure you become more productive and objective to the world around you.

As such this topic will help learners understand these fundamentals. More than this it will help them realize that access and inclusion go hand in hand together and unless a society moves ahead together it cannot really move at all.

Why are access and inclusion important

Now it's time to bring them both together. Though through the reviewing of the topics some connections were made this conclusive topic will help make them clearer. As technology advances more and more the online world becomes ever more crucial to succeeding.

Source: Defindia.org

Limited income and lack of know-how translate to barriers for many people in using the internet while gapping deeper into the hole of the poverty trap. This is so as educational opportunities left alone to the physical presence or outdated equipment means a true second class of citizens is been created and left permanently there. This is why Access to the internet has gained much momentum in being viewed as a human right. Indeed, according to the UN, such ⁴access should be right-based and user-centred while provided to all groups of people unconditionally.

What this essentially means is that it should be free. In other words, not only must countries ensure adequate same access, but the user must also be free to use it and express themselves without being afraid of any privacy breaches by fearful governments and private entities.

The right to be forgotten is a very good example to illustrate this. The same is true of the recent EU GDPR rule that set a tighter framework for the storing and processing of personal data.

⁴ <https://www.un.org/en/chronicle/article/government-policy-internet-must-be-rights-based-and-user-centred>

As such Access and inclusion are gaining much momentum. Given that progress can only be served by utilizing every resource in the economy, the term is used here in the broader sense beyond the fiscal and monetary, while ensuring that every voice and thought is given a fair try.

Doing so will have an immediate effect both in the digital and the physical world. Democracy for example cannot survive if there is a divide between the digital and physical world.

If access and inclusion are barred in the digital environment, it will be so in the physical one as well. When we operate a certain way in one the consequences transfer to the other. If one is being oppressed or oppresses in the digital, chances are this will be repeated in the physical as well. Innovation which is fundamental to our civilization could not have come about where innovators were stopped from speaking their minds, freely exploring concepts and taking input from a variety of people. No one is an island and we are collective creatures which, much like ants, need that synergy created in the mass of its peers.

Case study - Cornwall's digital inclusion programme

In Cornwall, 24% of adults were digitally excluded. This is so as they lacked basic digital skills. Thus, a team of Online Support Officers worked with communities to deliver a Basic Digital Skills training⁵ that reached 1,500 people since 2014. Below are two testimonials.

“SC from Camborne (93) – wanted to get online to learn how to shop and also to keep in touch with friends and family. SC had never used the internet before attending 4 sessions at the Camborne library. After the course had finished SC had met 1 new friend and considered that his life was better after learning to use the internet. When asked “what did you enjoy about this course and using the internet” his comments were “a magnificent glimpse at the extreme possibilities that can open.”

“MB from Liskeard (45) – wanted to learn about the internet and gain general computer skills. MB had never used the internet before attending 4 sessions at Liskeard Library no computer or broadband at home and no intention of getting either. After the course, MB reported “a whole new world opened up to me” and stated that they planned to get internet access at home within the next 3 months”.

Self-reflection: How could you help others to improve their basic digital skills?

Why are access and inclusion skills important

As already mention Access and Inclusion are the bedrocks of any concept of true digital citizenship. It is impossible to harvest all the benefits modern technology has to offer without these. As such, there are a plethora of relevant skills that needs to be developed at the individual and the institutional level.

Though the list is long some of the key competence that needs to be developed include:

- Internet skills: the ability to connect to the internet and go online
- Media skills: the ability to navigate various forms and tools of online contend
- Technical skills: the ability to use the internet and online services in an optimum way

⁵ <https://www.cornwall.gov.uk/media/31110590/case-study-13-digital-inclusion-programme.pdf> and <https://www.cornwall.gov.uk/community-and-living/digital-inclusion/#:~:text=Digital%20Inclusion%20is%20about%20making,and%20people%20around%20the%20world>

- Safety skills: the ability to navigate safely the internet and avoid such things as spam and hacking
- Confidence: the ability to truly represent your thoughts and feeling online
- Motivation: understanding why access and inclusion are important to all

Exercise 1: In the other's shoes

Objective:

- Understand why Access and Inclusions are important
- understand the impact of access and inclusion
- Provide feedback

Duration: 25 minutes

Tools: pen, piece of paper / forum

Methods: classroom discussions, description, comparison,

Description of the exercise: Write down what your dream job would be. Now Imagine that you saw somewhere an ad that you believed was tailor-made for you. You want to apply for this job but for some unbeknown reason, perhaps you were cursed, you have been deprived of internet access for a week. Applications are due in 6 days and you can't remember where you saw this ad or what the company's name was. Write down what you would do.

Tasks:

- Write down your dream job. Think big
- Imagine that you have been deprived of any internet access.
- You cannot remember where you saw the ad. Only that you were perfect for it
- Write down what you would do.
- Present it to your colleagues.
- While you present your list, the teacher will consolidate it with all answers given by your classmates.
- Compare your list with the consolidated list. Did they find solutions you did not think about? That is the power of access

Debriefing: The trainer emphasizes the fact that all the solutions came from different answers and all benefited from it.

Lessons learned: Access and Inclusion are important in terms of both giving and receiving.

Forum

Objectives:

- Identify barriers to access and inclusion
- give feedback
- Recommend solutions

You may write down all barriers to Access and Inclusion you can think of. Please also recommend solutions to it.

Tasks:

- Write down barriers to access and inclusion
- Write down solutions to your found Barriers
- Provide feedback to your classmates

Supplementary reading

UNESCO-Pearson Ten case studies on Digital inclusion: <https://en.unesco.org/themes/literacy-all/pearson-initiative/case-studies>

2. Module 2 - Are we all prejudiced

Snapshot

Summary: This topic deals with the concept of prejudice in an objective light. It touches upon such issues as how our minds are wired to perceive the world around us, why understanding this is important as well as exploring ways to reduce our own prejudice.

Key Takeaways:

- Understand how the mind is set up to group others into categories
- Discover ways to help train against it

How our mind works

We, humans, are social animals. We are undeniably designed to be part of a group. At the centre of it all are the core family, parents, and children. Expanding a little bit, we will find grandparents aunts' uncles and nephews. Beyond that is the friend circle, more out there are our colleagues, furthermore to this circle are people we happen to know, then there are the people that people we know, know, then the inhabitants of the same city, state, country, nation, union, culture, continent and finally the human race as a whole.

Beyond this, also consider that each one of us belongs to a different circle. Taking the example of the traditional family, the parents and children will belong to gender groups, age groups, political groups, friend circles, sports groups, various interest groups, and so on.

It is really quite astonishing that the mind can keep track of all these circles and groups. But just how exactly does it do it? The answer will come as a surprise. Prejudice. The mind assigns a person to all these groups almost instantaneously. Having assigned a person to these groups will also attribute to

the person the characteristics shared by that group. These could be good or bad depending on our perception of what these groups have as their characteristics.

There are generally speaking 3 types of prejudice. Always remember that we use the word prejudice here in a neutral sense, meaning a type of pre-impression we have. As such, prejudice can be good or bad and even⁶ includes such things as stereotypes or discrimination. This can be based on many things and range from innocent predisposition to hardcore discrimination and fanaticism. Examples of this include:

- Racism: The belief of superiority or inferiority of a specific race including the attribution of specific characteristics, bad or good to that race
- Sexism: The Belief of Superiority or inferiority of a specific gender including the attribution of specific characteristics, bad or good to that gender
- Class distinction: The Belief of Superiority or inferiority of a specific class of people such as low income including the attribution of specific characteristics, bad or good to that class
- Ageism: The Belief of Superiority or inferiority of a specific age group of people such as old including the attribution of specific characteristics, bad or good to that group
- Sexual Preferences: The Belief of Superiority or inferiority of a specific class of people based on their sexual preferences including the attribution of specific characteristics, bad or good to that group
- Homophobia: When prejudice about sexual preference amounts to hardcore discriminatory beliefs based solely on the sexual said preferences of the person then this translates to homophobia and is one of the most popular types of discrimination
- Cultural racism: That can involve any type of active negative prejudice inherent in a society such as a caste system of beliefs

As such the nature of prejudice is very broad indeed. Whether any form of prejudice good or bad should be tolerated is a matter of discussion. What is important to understand here is the inherent nature of prejudice. In fact, this is very much a characteristic of all of us. Some experts⁷ consider it learned while others consider it innate⁸ or a combination of both.

This course aims to illustrate that only by first accepting that prejudice is not beyond us can we improve ourselves.

How to combat prejudice

Being prejudiced is normal and cannot be helped. Nobody is perfect and we have to accept that. What is important is the degree we do it to and whether or not it rises to the level of discrimination and whether that causes harm to the other person.

This is very important. When we base our choices on our inherent or tough biases then we can really cause harm to a person. As Dr Charles Stangor (University of Maryland) argues: “Discrimination influences the daily life of its victims in areas such as employment, income, financial opportunities, housing, educational opportunities, and medical care.”. He goes on to note that what we actually do

⁶ <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/intropsychmaster/chapter/prejudice-and-discrimination/>

⁷ <https://news.harvard.edu/gazette/story/2013/11/fighting-prejudice-by-admitting-it/>

⁸ <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2005/05/050525105357.htm#:~:text=Summary%3A,our%20prehistor,ic%20ancestors%20from%20danger.>

is to try and suppress our way of thinking unsuccessfully as we are only able to do it for a short while. There are however many techniques to employ to reduce this disposition.

To this we can for example try not to react in our usual manner. This is not about suppressing stereotypes. It is about exposure to a different pattern so that gradually by consciously reacting in a less prejudicial way we become better at being less prejudiced. Another way is to think about people of a particular stereotype and then think about a person who despite sharing that characteristic does not fit the stereotype. Participating in cultural diversity and other relevant courses is also a great way to go about it. Another is trying to find the weak points in social norms that dictate an expected reaction based on the prejudice they describe and in general try to enable our judgmental inner voice to become critical in what it shares with us.

Case Study - The Bogota Doll

Using a simple doll in a Bogota classroom, one teacher began the country's most successful anti-racism program. The teacher brought a simple black toy baby doll to school, in the school's uniform and introduced her as a new classmate. The students were asked to protect and care for their new classmate taking turns to host the doll at their house. Soon even the families of the children began caring for the doll. The project is now been implemented at other schools across the country: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D7wB9UMgXG8>

Self-reflection: What attitudes would you expect to have been developed by students while taking care of the doll?

Why is understanding and reducing prejudice important

If we cannot accept our prejudice, we cannot confront it. Nobody is beyond it if even for a speckle of it. When we accept the prejudice in us whether inherent or learned, it becomes easier to see it and accept it in others. This means we will be less slighted when prejudiced against as we can know that some level of prejudice is unavoidable and perhaps like us that another person is working on it. Learning to confront and working on reducing it can take us down wonderful paths of acceptance and enlightenment while transforming us into a beacon of change for others beyond ourselves.

Though the list is long some of the key competence that needs to be developed include:

- Self-awareness skills: the ability to become more critical of ourselves
- Media skills: the ability to navigate various forms and tools of online content with a softer eye which could be borderline offensive but in an unintentional way

- Empowerment: The ability to better be able to understand the inner working of your mind and guide you to desired results
- Empathy: To be more in touch with other people's feelings
- Conflict resolution: To be able to soften discussions by understanding that the person was not intentionally offensive
- Confidence: the ability to truly represent your thoughts and feeling online
- Motivation: understanding that prejudice is a part of us all and working on reducing it

Exercise 2: Strangers no more

Objective:

- Understand that Prejudice is part of us all
- Enable self-reflection
- Provide feedback

Duration: 15 minutes

Tools: pen, piece of paper/forum

Methods: classroom discussions, description, comparison,

Description of the exercise: Say for example you meet a person for the first time. Take a deep breath and begin writing down in bullet points all the things you notice about them in the turn they come to your mind.

Tasks:

- Write down whatever and all the things you believe you would notice in this person in the order you notice them. It could be anything
- Share it with your colleagues.
- While you present your list, the teacher will consolidate it with all answers given by your classmates. Teachers also add their own characteristics

Debriefing: The trainer emphasizes the fact that all these characteristics are noticeable to all of us whether consciously or unconsciously. Depending on the beliefs we attach to these characteristics a judgment is made of the person comprised of the totality of the characteristics as an average.

Lessons learned: Prejudice is unavoidable and acceptance through self-reflection could be a good start to combat it.

Forum

Objectives:

- Share prejudices that you are aware exist
- give feedback
- Recommend ways to improve

You may write down any prejudices you are aware of no matter how small. Please also ways to improve them.

Tasks:

- Write down known prejudices

Erasmus+

ATHENS
LIFELONG
LEARNING
INSTITUTE

4 TEAM 4
excellence

SEAL
CYPRUS

- Write down ways to address them

Supplementary reading

Principles of Social Psychology, Dr Charles Stangor:

<https://opentextbc.ca/socialpsychology/chapter/reducing-discrimination/>

3. Module 3 - Democracy and the digital

Snapshot

Summary: This topic deals with the fundamentals of Digital Democracy. It examines how the two interact, why it's important to maintain democracy in both the physical and the digital world as well as finding ways to improve their effects.

Key Takeaways:

- Understanding digital democracy
- Understanding the interaction of the two

How democracy works

Those of us that live in democratic societies might take personal freedom for granted. However, this is not the global case. According to⁹ the "EIU Democracy Index 2019 - World Democracy Report" no more than about half of the countries in the world are democratic. In fact, out of the 167 countries surveyed just 75 had some sort of democracy in place. The number drops to just 22 if we differentiated between full democracies and flawed democracies.

The distinction is important. The elements that comprise the index and the definitions can better illustrate this. There are 60 questions to be answered, some by expert analysts and others by the general public. These belong to five categories namely:

- electoral process and pluralism
- civil liberties
- the functioning of government
- political participation

⁹ Available at <https://www.eiu.com/topic/democracy-index>

- political culture.

Some questions carry more weight than others. These include:

- Whether national elections are free and fair
- The security of voters
- The influence of foreign powers on government
- The capability of the civil servants to implement policies

As such and based on the score (1 No democracy-9 full democracy) the following categories of democracy are assigned:

- Full democracies that cater to civil liberties and political freedoms are supported and upheld by a relevant political culture.
 - Norway is at the Top
- Flawed democracies where basic civil liberties are upheld and elections are free but some minor to moderate issues prevent them from being categorized as full democracies, for example, some sort of media freedom interferences or underdeveloped political culture
 - Greece is a good example
- Hybrid regimes do not rise to the level of authoritarian regimes but major issues prevent them from becoming even flawed democracies such as election fraud, major cases of oppression coupled with such things as corruption and major lack or fear of political involvement as well as other such similar characteristics
 - Ukraine is a good example
- Authoritarian regimes were no democracy and personal freedom could really be said to exist
 - North Korea is at the bottom

As such Democracy should not be taken for granted. The questions that make up the index also reveal to us many of the characteristics of how democracy works or ought to work. Far from relying on an abstract government to enforce and guarantee civil liberties and a functioning system of government, it is up to each and every one of us to develop the political culture to be actively engaged and inspire others to do so likewise. You'd be perhaps surprised to find out that even the USA which often champions itself as the land of the free is considered to be a flawed democracy.

How the digital makes democracy better

To be able to harvest all the benefits of technology access and inclusion are essential. Nowhere perhaps is this truer than e-democracy, a term taken to mean the electronic form of democracy or ICT technology used to digitize government and citizen interactions. However, the term has been expanded to include democratic processes that are followed in the digital world.

This can include simple things as well as complex hive mind decisions that can affect the globe. From scheduling a meeting among fellows through the use of doodle voting to setting the price of silver on a day-by-day basis technology and democracy interloop and enrich each other constantly.

Of course, to all this access and inclusion are crucial. Setting up an appointment between coworkers is meaningless if everyone is not invited to vote on their availability.

Setting prices for commodities and shares on the stock markets is pointless unless all relevant platforms, dealers, merchants, stockbrokers, stock markets, and so on are consulted and invited to vote. Here the concept of the vote is used in the metaphoric sense of voting through buying and selling

at specific prices. Truly every time we buy something we cast a vote in favour of that thing and against the thing we don't buy. Many companies have lost billions because consumer boycotts brought about a specific event or image that had negative pupil consequences.

Yet this automatic voting does not limit itself to just buying and selling. Indeed, the world is full of examples of how democracy, Access and Inclusion, and the digital element combine together to produce and help flourish modern democracies.

A powerful article for example shared by a lot of people can have dire consequences on an offender. Of course, they can also have negative consequences on someone who did nothing wrong, to begin with. This is the type of balance and safeguards that need to be put in place to truly combine the digital with democracy and ensure its benefits to them. As such and given our ability to regulate digital solutions could be said to have an overall positive predisposition towards democracy and democratic societies.

More than this they help ease the tension among less democratic countries' citizens. They also help these countries progress to the next stage of democratic evolution. Just think of the current course. Provided you have a device capable of internet connection you can, no matter where you are or who you are have the same access and be included in the course. The forum itself ensures your voice is heard and you get a say in how the module is conducted.

Case study - Decide Madrid

The Decide Madrid initiative is an online platform. Here the citizens of the City work with government officials to help decide such things as the city budget while being able to submit proposals and participate in local decision-making processes of the city:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t1wAE9JRe9Q>

Self-reflection: What would you tell your local Government to improve in the area of digitalization?

Why are democracy and the digital important together

The principles of democracy must be rooted in the digital world. This is because though technology has the power to greatly support democracies it also has the power to suppress people when used for purposes by autocratic governments. The potential for abuse is great and only by transferring democratic values such as openness, dialogue, joint decision making, liberty, civil rights, and so on into the digital can the idea of Access and Inclusion be fully supported. We have already covered its importance in module one above.

Though the list is long some of the key competencies that need to be developed include:

- Self-awareness skills: the ability to become more critical of ourselves on how we support the democratic principles we aspire to in our daily lives
- Media skills: the ability to navigate various forms and tools of online content with a more open mind respecting each other's right to expression and so on

- Empowerment: The ability to better be able to understand the importance of democracy and how technology can be a force of good
- Openness and acceptance: To recognize each other's freedom to be their own person
- Confidence: the ability to expect to be heard while listening to others
- Motivation: understanding the importance of maintaining democratic values

Exercise 3: Democracy at risk

Objective:

- Understand the importance of Democracy
- Understand obstacles and provide solutions to address the democratic deficit
- Provide feedback

Duration: 25 minutes

Tools: pen, piece of paper / forum

Methods: classroom discussions, description, comparison,

Description of the exercise: In the country you currently live in, what would you say is the state of Democracy? Are digital solutions applied to remedy some of the problems? Write down your observations and suggestions to improve

Tasks:

- Write down what you believe the state of democracy is in the county you currently live in
- Write down obstacles to democracy you observe in the country you live in
- Write down solutions to these problems
- Share it with your colleagues.
- While you present your list, the teacher will consolidate it with all answers given by your classmates. The teacher also adds own observations

Debriefing: The trainer emphasizes once more the importance of democracy. It explains to learners that through the exercise we could see democracy in action through the exchanges of opinions. Technology was the medium that enabled this sort of discussion.

Lessons learned: Democracy is important and its principles must be transferred to the online environment.

Forum

Objectives:

- Share different types of government types that you are aware exist
- give feedback

You may write down any types of government that you think works or not.

Tasks:

- Write down known forms of government
- Write down examples

Supplementary reading

Principles of Social Psychology, Dr. Charles Stangor:

<https://opentextbc.ca/socialpsychology/chapter/reducing-discrimination/>

4. Module 4 - Trolls and other creatures of the net

Snapshot

Summary: This topic deals with the fundamental danger of the digital world. It touches upon such issues as are what is trolling, fake news and so on while exploring the netiquette of things that is what you should and shouldn't do in the digital world.

Key Takeaways:

- Understanding what constitutes acceptable behaviour
- Understanding the effects that unacceptable behaviour has on access and inclusion

Unacceptable behaviours, from bullying to fake news

The digital world is its own environment. With it as with any environment, there are things you can and can't do. This is the so-called netiquette of things.

Unlike the physical world, the digital world provides more of a hiding place. It provides more anonymity and enhanced protection from the consequences of one's actions. Things that might be ok in the digital world, like engaging in certain acts while playing a violent game, are not ok in the physical world. So exactly how does one begin to list all acceptable behaviour and where to draw the line is the matter of much debate recently.

Despite this, there are some universally accepted Yes' and No's:

- Online bullying included repetitive intentionally harmful behaviour such as making threats and using derogative remarks
- Sharing fake news, that is make sure the story you share is credible
- Inappropriate comments which are similar to online bullying expect that they are not repetitive behaviour at least not with regard to the same person
- Hate speech that is inciting others into sharing racial viewpoints and even inciting violence
- Uploading inappropriate illegal material such as unlicensed music

- Accessing inappropriate sites such as torrent sites
- Stalking such as always wanting to know the location of others or obsessing about a person to the point that you view everything they do and try to become engaged in their online persona in a manner that has not been reciprocated
- Breaching copyright laws such as downloading ripped movies
- Trolling such as when intentionally trying to aggravate people
- Spamming such as when posting unwanted adds
- Hacking such as accessing without prior consent other's online accounts

Beyond these, the netiquette of things should always be kept in mind, including:

- Make sure when you are with people you are not also online, that is not ignoring people next to you
- Be respectful and remember messages often lose their content in the digital world as they are accompanied by non-verbal communication
- Don't share everything online as when it's out there it's out there
- Be inclusive in your comments, that is make sure everyone can get what you are saying
- Be wary of people you meet online not everyone is really your friend
- Fact check the content and don't share spam and fake stories
- Allow others their right to be their own person

The internet of things is a vast chaotic place. Learning how to behave online involves a range of new skills and competencies. These will be covered in the course of the project. For now, and for this module, the intent is to cover the acceptable behaviour you should have and expect from others.

What you should know about the dangers of the digital world

The digital world can be a beautiful thing. However, and given that it is hard to regulate it and observe those regulations it can also be a very dangerous place. From hackers bent on stealing private information and access codes to trolls looking to aggravate it is good to practice some precautions and safe habits to navigate the net with more peace of mind. Of course, a lot could be said on this topic but some of the most important ones in terms of bad habits include:

- Always using the same password on all sites and devices while never updating the password
- Not having an antivirus and anti-malware program
- Not updating the antivirus software and not using a proper software
- Not having a computer password
- Clicking on every ad you see and links provided by people you don't know
- Using HTTP sites as opposed to HTTPS as the first is not secured and the second is
- Checking your bank account or other sensitive data on a public WIFI
- Not investing time to have a strong WIFI password
- Agreeing to all terms on software install that may include a range of other products ready to be installed

These are good things to keep in mind. In general, precautions¹⁰ you should learn to take include:

- Consider the source
- Read beyond the headline
- Check the author

¹⁰ <https://www.factcheck.org/2016/11/how-to-spot-fake-news/>

- See if the claim is supported
- Check the date
- Ask whether this is some kind of joke
- Check your biases
- Consult the experts
- Advise Fact-checking sites

It is also worth noting that the most effective kind of hacking is social hacking. Far from the classic image of the hacker sitting in a dark room inside some basement writing up codes to infect systems to extract information most people's accounts get compromised by willingly giving up crucial information and access codes to their accounts. Those that engage in such activities are numerous and have had tons of experience in gaining the confidence of online users. They may appear as friends or even government employees and can be very persuasive. So, keep in mind that social hacking is a real thing.

Case study – Hacking techniques

Watch this short video on 5 of the most popular hacking techniques and how to prevent them:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=raqVtLw_1LQ

Self-reflection: Were you ever subject to any of these hacking techniques? If so, what did you do?

Why should you beware of using the internet

As it was said, the internet can be a very fun and useful tool. Many of us would simply be lost without it. However, it can be a very dangerous and harmful place. As more and more people expand the hours, they spend online vis-a-vis the physical world the potential for harm increases in both the sense of causing and receiving. This is not only about the intentional harm. Though you may have the best intentions in the world you could still accidentally cause harm to a person and them to you without ever meaning to.

Though the list is long some of the key competence that needs to be developed include:

- Netiquette: The moral and proper way to behave online
- Awareness: To know the dangers of the internet
- empowerment: To be able to guard against the dangers of the internet
- Digital Empathy: to be able to protect others by being aware of the danger they might be putting themselves into and to guard yourself against behaviour that could cause harm to others
- Media skills: the ability to navigate various forms and tools of online content safer
- Confidence: the ability to more freely navigate the net
- Motivation: understanding the importance of navigating safely the web

Exercise 4: White hat and black hat hackers

Objective:

- Understand the importance of staying safe online
- Understand that not all hacking is necessarily bad and use critical thinking
- Provide feedback

Erasmus+

ATHENS
LIFELONG
LEARNING
INSTITUTE

4 TEAM 4
excellence

SEAL
CYPRUS

Duration: 15 minutes

Tools: pen, piece of paper / forum

Methods: classroom discussions, description, comparison,

Description of the exercise: Ask yourself if all hacking is bad. In the world of the net, there are so-called white hat and black hat hackers. The term is taken from old western movies where the bad guy would be wearing a black hat and the good guy a white one. Think for example of wiki leaks. Ask yourself if that could have been a white hat hacking or not. Write down your opinion as well as other instances and examples of what could be white and black hat hacking.

Tasks:

- Write down if you believe that some hacking could be good
- Give some examples they don't have to be real cases
- Share it with your colleagues.
- While you present your list, the teacher will consolidate it with all answers given by your classmates. Teachers also add their observations

Debriefing:

Trainer emphasizes once more the fact that not all hacking is necessarily bad. There is an instance where this could be beneficial to the world and the greater good.

Lessons learned: types of dangers online technology could be used in many ways bad or good.

Forum

Objectives:

- Share different types of online risks that you are aware of
- give feedback

You may write down any types of risks you are aware of and ways to protect against these.

Tasks:

- Write down the types of risks
- Write down ways to protect

Supplementary reading

One of the top antivirus providers' recommendations about staying safe online:

<https://usa.kaspersky.com/resource-center/preemptive-safety/top-10-internet-safety-rules-and-what-not-to-do-online>

5. Module 5 - Become an access and inclusion champion

Snapshot

Summary: This topic deals with the fundamentals of what it means to be a digital champion for good. It touches upon such issues as what you should know to protect yourself, how to protect others, and its importance as well as explores the requirements of achieving this concept truly.

Key Takeaways:

- Understanding how to protect yourself and others
- Understanding what it takes to be a champion of the concept

Be the change

Mahatma Gandhi said: “Be the change you want to see in the world”. No, he actually did not say that but it's good advice nonetheless to live by.

What he said was: “We but mirror the world. All the tendencies present in the outer world are to be found in the world of our body. If we could change ourselves, the tendencies in the world would also change. As a man changes his own nature, so does the attitude of the world change towards him. This is the divine mystery supreme. A wonderful thing it is and the source of our happiness. We need not wait to see what others do.”.

This is a good example of fact-checking. Though the first quote does not belong to Gandhi it does do a pretty good job of summarizing what he said and transforming it into a universal slogan that spiralled revolution in our way of thinking. The person that came up with the slogan is unknown. As far as we

know they were not a famous reformist or a celebrity role model. In essence, what they were was both the object and subject of change.

By this, we mean that this person whoever it was brought about a change in our ways of thinking by they themselves becoming change. A more tangible example would be that of a doctor fighting diseases in sub-Saharan Africa or a developer making their software open access. This is what is meant by be the change and implies that a person actively changes their pattern of thought and behaviour instead of waiting around for the world to change so that they too might experience that desired result.

This is the first step to becoming an access and inclusion champion. Practising it ourselves and when we do the world around us will begin to change little by little.

How to stay safe and protect others

The second step involves knowing how to be safe and protect others. Throughout this course, we went over such things as the importance of the digital, the dangers of the net, and many more.

All these now must come together and arm you with the skills necessary to do just that. To protect yourself and others to truly be an Access and Inclusion champion. What this means is to be able to protect yourself and others from things that prevent them and yourself from fully experiencing all the benefits of uninterrupted access and unconditional inclusion to the wonders of the digital world and the many opportunities it envelopes.

The list of things that would do that is long and we have but scratched the surface. They involve such things as privacy infringements, to protect against hate speech, spam, trolls, hackings, prejudice, non-democratic processes, restraints, technical barriers as well as non-technical and many more. All these now come together to form a solid knowledge database that you can call upon in this quest, we invite you to join in being an access and Inclusion champion.

A brave new world

The third step involves getting others to join the cause. By becoming the change and arming yourself with the know-how of Access and Inclusion, you can help and mentor others in doing the same so that the circle grows.

Now, this is not about running the streets protesting or becoming an overwhelmingly enthused activist to it all. Rather it is about small changes we can all make to our everyday life. Things that you wouldn't notice before this course perhaps.

This involves for example speaking up. When somebody online is making derogative remarks, you can come to their aid or report them to the systems admin and in most platforms, this is done anonymously instead of simply passing it by.

More and more platforms especially show less and less tolerance for things like spam and hate speech. This is especially true for social media and we consider this is a sign of the things to come.

All around the EU, there is an uproar. Every day, member states within the EU enhance their efforts to actively take more and more measures to combat phenomena that would bar Access and Inclusion for all. In essence, you are not alone, but in very good company. So, you get to be part of the solution.

Erasmus+

ATHENS
LIFELONG
LEARNING
INSTITUTE

4 TEAM 4
excellence

SEAL
CYPRUS

Case study - Storming of the United States Capitol

On January 6, 2021, in Washington, a mob of protesters stormed the US Capitol. This quickly turned into a riot that led to the evacuation and lockdown of the Capitol, and five deaths in total. The mob was made up of supporters of President Donald Trump in an attempt to overturn his defeat in the 2020 presidential election which they claimed had been compromised. The rest have been extracted from Wikipedia:

“Called to action by Trump, thousands of his supporters gathered in Washington, D.C., on January 5 and 6 in support of his claim that the 2020 election had been "stolen" from him, and to demand that Vice President Mike Pence and Congress reject President-elect Joe Biden's victory. On the morning of January 6, at a "Save America" rally on the Ellipse, Rudy Giuliani called for "trial by combat"; Donald Trump Jr. threatened the president's opponents by saying "we're coming for you", having previously called for "total war"; and Trump repeated his false claims about election irregularities and told the crowd to "fight like hell". At the president's encouragement, thousands of the crowd then walked to the Capitol, where a joint session of Congress was beginning the Electoral College vote count to formalize Biden's victory.”. No one saw this coming and it was the power of the digital world that enabled these events to take place.

Read the whole story here:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2021_storming_of_the_United_States_Capitol#:~:text=The%20storming%20of%20the%20United,in%20the%202020%20presidential%20election

Self-reflection: How can the use of the digital world lead to public unrest?

Why is becoming an access an inclusion champion important

The world does not change the way we want it to by itself. We have to be active and proactive in bringing about the positive change we want to see. It all starts with us.

When we feel strongly about something we cannot just sit around and do nothing. A cause needs its champions and when we want that cause to succeed, we have to be its champions, everyone to the extent that they can do so and this will, in turn, inspire others to do the same.

Though the list is long some of the key competencies that need to be developed include:

- Self-awareness skills: the ability to become more critical of ourselves and realize our strength
- Media skills: the ability to navigate various forms and tools of online content with a willingness to correct wrongs we see and avoid causing unintentional harm to others.

- Empowerment: the ability to help ourselves and help others whose rights of Access and Inclusion have been infringed upon
- Empathy: To be more in touch with other people's feelings and be more able to motivate them
- Confidence: the ability to stand up for your rights and others
- Motivation: understanding that access and inclusion is a cause worth protecting

Exercise 5: Use and abuse

Objective:

- Understand that being a champion is not always a clear case
- Enable self-reflection, critical thinking
- Provide feedback

Duration: 15 minutes

Tools: pen, piece of paper / forum

Methods: classroom discussions, description, comparison,

Description of the exercise: Recently Donald Trump has been banned from most social media. The platforms some of them at least went even as far as deleting his accounts. Some people argue in favour while others are against it. On the other hand, is freedom of expression and on the other inciting to violence. Both sides would seem to have their pros and cons. In the end, it is all a balancing act perhaps between these two. Where do you stand? Please provide arguments.

Tasks:

- Write down whatever you believe the platforms should or should not have banned Trump from their sides.
- Write down arguments to support your position. Feel free to also write arguments against it.
- Share it with your colleagues.
- While you present your list, the teacher will consolidate it with all answers given by your classmates. Teachers also add their own characteristics

Debriefing: The trainer emphasizes the fact that being a champion is not easy. Most times it is a balancing act and it is up to each one of us to find our own morality and where they draw the line.

Lessons learned: The net can be used and abused. As such, Access and Inclusion can only go so far. The line between the two is always clear and as such one must really understand the concepts to see more clearly the boundaries.

Forum

Objectives:

- Share other cases you know that may have caused people to become a violent mob
- give feedback on whether Access and Inclusion should be absolute
- Recommend ways to improve such violent situations and limit their occurrences

You may write down any cases you know where uninterrupted Access and inclusion resulted in harm to others.

Tasks:

- Write down known cases no matter how big or small
- Write down ways to help prevent them

Supplementary reading

How to motivate others to do good a Tedtalk:

https://www.ted.com/talks/erez_yoeli_how_to_motivate_people_to_do_good_for_others?language=en

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2021_storming_of_the_United_States_Capitol#:~:text=The%20storming%20of%20the%20United,in%20the%202020%20presidential%20election.

6. Assessment quizzes

Module 1

- 1) Access means:
 - a) Having the ability to use online environments
 - b) Both the competence and the infrastructure to use online environments
 - c) Knowing your password

- 2) Inclusion means:
 - a) Feeling part of the online environment and allowing others to feel the same
 - b) Asking your friend to like your pages
 - c) Making lots of online friends

- 3) Globally, how many people had access to the internet in 2018?
 - a) Just 50.7% of the world population
 - b) Just 10.7% of the world population
 - c) Just 80.7% of the world population

- 4) To celebrate Diversity means, for example:
 - a) Promoting certain disadvantaged backgrounds
 - b) Reduce certain advantaged background
 - c) Accepting different backgrounds

Module 2

- 1) Are all people prejudiced?
 - a) People are not prejudiced
 - b) In one way or another positive or negative people are prejudiced
 - c) Some people are prejudiced some are not

- 2) Humans are social animals:
 - a) Yes and they have an ever-expanding circle with different levels of intimacy
 - b) People only live in small groups
 - c) Only some who like to be popular

- 3) At the core of our social circle are:
 - a) All people we know
 - b) Usually are the immediate family
 - c) Friends and co-workers

- 4) About your prejudice:
 - a) All people are born prejudiced and they never change
 - b) It is only a positive one so I don't need to change it
 - c) You can decrease it if you accept it and work on improving

Module 3

- 1) Are all countries true democracies?
 - a) Very few countries in the world are true democracies
 - b) No country can really be called democratic
 - c) Most of the countries in the world are true democracies

- 2) The most important thing for democracies is:
 - a) Elections to be fair
 - b) Members of government to have high salaries
 - c) To be no corruption

- 3) Flawed democracies:
 - a) Are the same as real democracies
 - b) Are similar to real democracies but still have some minor issues
 - c) There are no flawed democracies

- 4) Being democratic:
 - a) Involves only politics
 - b) Is not something you can try and do
 - c) Means you apply the democratic principle in your everyday life

Module 4

- 1) Online bullying means:
 - a) Being impolite on occasions

Erasmus+

ATHENS
LIFELONG
LEARNING
INSTITUTE

4 TEAM 4
excellence

SEAL
CYPRUS

- b) Is not a real thing
 - c) Being repetitively harmful towards someone
- 2) Being safe online means:
- a) Staying well informed of the dangers inherent in the digital world
 - b) Only using a different password every now and then
 - c) There are no dangers in the digital world
- 3) When you find some media online
- a) It has to be true
 - b) You have to carefully assess a number of factors
 - c) Always feel free to share what you find online with others
- 4) No one is watching me when I use the web:
- a) The web is a very private place
 - b) Some people and a lot of machines are very interested in what I do
 - c) Only advertisers care about my online behaviour

Module 5

- 1) Being the change really means:
- a) Care only about yourself
 - b) Try to change the world
 - c) Change yourself so that the world changes
- 2) Being a digital champion:
- a) Try to protect yourself and others by ingrowing of any dangers you see
 - b) Means only looking after yourself
 - c) Only care about major internet criminals
- 3) Access and inclusion:
- a) Are not important
 - b) Are very much important and relate to each other
 - c) Are very different and have nothing to do with each other

- 4) Staying moral online:
- a) Only applies to others
 - b) Is not important
 - c) Applies to yourself and others

7. References

CGTN America, 2019, The Bogota Doll, available at:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D7wB9UMgXG8>

Council of Europe, 2019, Digital Citizenship Education Handbook

Cornwall council digital Inclusion Programme, 2019, available at:

<https://www.cornwall.gov.uk/media/31110590/case-study-13-digital-inclusion-programme.pdf>

Cornwall council digital Inclusion, 2019, available at: [https://www.cornwall.gov.uk/community-and-living/digital-](https://www.cornwall.gov.uk/community-and-living/digital-inclusion/#:~:text=Digital%20Inclusion%20is%20about%20making,and%20people%20around%20the%20world)

[inclusion/#:~:text=Digital%20Inclusion%20is%20about%20making,and%20people%20around%20the%20world](https://www.cornwall.gov.uk/community-and-living/digital-inclusion/#:~:text=Digital%20Inclusion%20is%20about%20making,and%20people%20around%20the%20world)

Digidem Lab, 2020, Decide Madrid, available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t1wAE9JRe9Q>

Dr. Charles Stangor, Principles of Social Psychology, Dr. Charles Stangor, available at:

<https://opentextbc.ca/socialpsychology/chapter/reducing-discrimination/>

Eurostat 2020, Digital Economy, available at:

[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statisticsexplained/index.php/Digital_economy_and_society_statistics__households_and_individuals#:~:text=Planned%20article%20update%3A%20September%202021.&text=By%202019%2C%20the%20share%20of,in%202009%20\(55%20%25\).](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statisticsexplained/index.php/Digital_economy_and_society_statistics__households_and_individuals#:~:text=Planned%20article%20update%3A%20September%202021.&text=By%202019%2C%20the%20share%20of,in%202009%20(55%20%25).)

Harvard Gazette, Fighting prejudice by admitting it, available at:

<https://news.harvard.edu/gazette/story/2013/11/fighting-prejudice-by-admitting-it/>

James Stanfield, How To Promote Inclusion In The Classroom, available at: <https://stanfield.com/11-strategies-promote-inclusion-in-the-classroom/>

Kaspersky, 2021, Top 10 Internet Safety Rules & What Not to Do Online, available at:

<https://usa.kaspersky.com/resource-center/preemptive-safety/top-10-internet-safety-rules-and-what-not-to-do-online>

Lumen, Introduction to Psychology, available at:

<https://courses.lumenlearning.com/intropsychmaster/chapter/prejudice-and-discrimination/>

Science news, 2015, Prejudice Is Hard-wired Into The Human Brain, available at:

<https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2005/05/050525105357.htm#:~:text=Summary%3A,our%20prehistoric%20ancestors%20from%20danger.>

Teck in Asia, 2020, 5 of the most popular hacking techniques and how to prevent them, available at:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=raqVtLw_1LQ

Tedtalk, How to motivate people to do good for others, available at:

https://www.ted.com/talks/erez_yoeli_how_to_motivate_people_to_do_good_for_others?language=en

The Economist, 2019, Democracy Index, available at: <https://www.eiu.com/topic/democracy-index>

UNESCO, 2017. Pearson, Ten case studies on Digital inclusion, available at:

<https://en.unesco.org/themes/literacy-all/pearson-initiative/case-studies> United nations

Internet must be Rights based and user centered, available at:

<https://www.un.org/en/chronicle/article/government-policy-internet-must-be-rights-based-and-user-centred>

Wikipedia, 2021, Storming the Unites states capitol, available

at:https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2021_storming_of_the_United_States_Capitol#:~:text=The%20storming%20of%20the%20United,in%20the%202020%20presidential%20election

World Bank, 2019, Internet Users index, available at:

<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/IT.NET.USER.ZS>

Factcheck.org, 2016, How to spot fake news, available at: <https://www.factcheck.org/2016/11/how-to-spot-fake-news/>

Erasmus+

ATHENS
LIFELONG
LEARNING
INSTITUTE

4 TEAM 4
excellence

SEAL
CYPRUS

Appendix

Assessment quiz check sheets

Evaluation quiz Module 1 check sheet – correct answers

1b

2a

3a

4c

Evaluation quiz Module 2 check sheet – correct answers

1b

2a

3b

4c

Evaluation quiz Module 3 check sheet – correct answers

1a

2a

3b

4c

Evaluation quiz Module 4 check sheet – correct answers

1c

2a

3b

4b

Evaluation quiz Module 5 check sheet – correct answers

1c

2a

3b

4c

Instructional design review checklist for youth workers

No	Criteria	Yes	No
1. Objectives			
1.1	Are objectives stated clearly for the learner?		
1.2	Are the course requirements consistent with the objectives?		
1.3	Do chapters/topics thoroughly cover the course's objectives?		
1.4	Do the learning objectives match the learning outcomes?		
1.5	Does the overall content and structure of the course meet its instructional objectives?		
2. Structure			
2.1	Does the course have a concise and comprehensive overview or syllabus?		
2.2	Does the course include examples, analogies, case studies, simulations, graphical representations, and interactive questions?		
2.3	Does the course structure use appropriate methods and procedures to measure student mastery?		
3. Content			
3.1	Does the content flow seamlessly, without grammatical, syntactical and typing errors?		
3.2	Is the content up-to-date?		
3.3	Is the content aligned with the curriculum?		
3.4	Are the desirable outcomes incorporated into the content?		
3.5	Is the content in compliance with copyright laws and all its quoted material cited correctly?		
3.6	Does the course engage students in critical and abstract thinking?		
3.7	Does the course have prerequisites or require a technical background?		
4. Assessment			
4.1	Are the assignments relevant, efficient and engage students in a variety of performance types and activities?		
4.2	Are practice and assessment questions interactive?		
4.3	Do the practice and assessment tasks focus on the course's objectives?		
5. Technology - Design			
5.1	Is the design clear and consistent, with appropriate directions?		
5.2	Are the images and graphics of high quality and suitable for the course?		
5.3	Is the course easy to navigate and offers assistance with technical and course management?		
5.4	Is the course navigation structure consistent and reliable?		
5.5	Are the course hardware and software defined?		
5.6	Are the audio and on-screen text in sync?		
5.7	Does the architecture of the course allow instructors to add content, activities and extra assessments?		

Feedback on topic for students

Assessment of Module						
Course title:						
Module Title:						
Part A:	On a scale of 1-5 where 1 is the lowest and 5 the highest level of agreement indicate how you feel on the following					
	Observations	1	2	3	4	5
1	The subject was interesting					
2	I believe the topics covered were important					
3	I would like to know more about the area					
4	I have learned new things which I am likely to apply in the future					
5	I would like to improve my skills in the area					
6	I am likely to recommend this course					
Part B:	In the space provided please feel free to include any comments and recommendations you wish to make					
Part C:	In the space provided please feel free to include your email address if you would like to be kept informed about this project					

